

ISic1028

I.Sicily inscription 1028

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication; list of
magistrates

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140507

1. ἐπὶ Ἡρακλείου τοῦ
2. Νυμφοδώρου
3. προστατεύσαν[τ]ες
4. Ἦραι καὶ Ἀφροδίται
5. Ἀριστόγειτος
6. Ἀρτέμων Πausανία
7. Διονυσόδωρος
8. Κρίθων Φιλιστίωνος
9. Φιλιστίων Σώσιος
10. Κλέων Νυμφοδώρου.
11. γραμματεῦς
12. Φιλιστίων.
- 13.

Edition: PHI175419

1. ἐπὶ Ἡρακλείου τοῦ
2. Νυμφοδώρου
3. προστατεύσαντες

4. Ἦραι καὶ Ἀφροδίται
5. Ἀριστόγειτος
6. Ἀρτέμων Πausανία
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8. Κρίθων Φιλιστίωνος
9. Φιλιστίων Σώσιος
10. Κλέων Νυμφοδώρου
11. γραμματεὺς
12. Φιλιστίων.
- 13.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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